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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF EFFECT OF INDOMETHACIN IN
PREVENTION OF POST-ERCP PANCREATITIS PATIENTS**¹Dr. Noreena Saba, ²Dr. Muhammad Usman Mazhar, ³Dr. Quratul Ain Akber,¹WMO at THQ Hospital, Yazman²MO at RHC Bamabala³Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur**Abstract:**

Introduction: Among the gastrointestinal endoscopic procedures, endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) has the greatest potential for complications. The most common complication is acute pancreatitis, with a reported overall incidence of 2%-10%; however, this can rise to 30% in the presence of certain risk factors. **Aims and objectives:** The basic aim of the study is to analyze the effect of Indomethacin in Prevention of Post-ERCP Pancreatitis patients. **Material and methods:** This randomized control study was conducted at THQ hospital, Yazman during 2018. There were total 200 patients who was selected for this study. Patients divided into two groups. One group was given per rectal indomethacin (2 suppositories 50 mg each) while other group given no suppositories. **Results:** A total of 200 cases fulfilling the inclusion/exclusion criteria were enrolled to compare the frequency of Post ERCP Pancreatitis in patients treated with or without rectal indomethacin. Age distribution of the patients was done, it shows that 30%(n=45) in Indomethacin and 29.33%(n=44) without Indomethacin group were between 15-50 years of age while 70%(n=105) in Indomethacin and 70.67%(n=106) without Indomethacin group were between 51-85 years of age, mean±SD was calculated as 56.28±8.39 and 55.72±7.84 years in both groups respectively. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that the frequency of Post ERCP Pancreatitis is significantly lower in patients treated with rectal indomethacin when compared to those without it.

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INTRODUCTION:

Among the gastrointestinal endoscopic procedures, endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) has the greatest potential for complications. The most common complication is acute pancreatitis, with a reported overall incidence of 2%-10%; however, this can rise to 30% in the presence of certain risk factors. Post-ERCP pancreatitis is most often mild, but in around 10% of the cases (0.4%-0.6% of the procedures performed) it is severe and potentially fatal [1]. The mortality rate is about 0.1%-0.5%. Furthermore, asymptomatic hyperamylasaemia occurs in 35%-70% of patients undergoing ERCP. The wide interval of the published incidence of pancreatitis can be explained by the different criteria used for the diagnosis, the type and duration of the follow-up of the patients involved in the studies, the level of endoscopic expertise and the frequencies of patient- and procedure-related risk factors among the investigated patient population [2].

Endoscopic Retrograde Pancreaticholangiography (ERCP) is one of the most commonly performed, most complex and high risk endoscopic procedure performed for the treatment of various conditions of biliary and pancreatic ductal system. ERCP has a higher potential for complications that range from mild, non-lethal incidents with immediate resolution to major life threatening crises [3]. A feared complication of ERCP is post-ERCP Pancreatitis (PEP) which occurs in 30 to 40 % of high risk patients.

PEP is defined as new or worsened abdominal pain and serum amylase level 3 times or more above the upper limit of normal, measured after 24 hours of the procedure. PEP is graded as mild, moderate and severe depending on length of hospital stay & complications of the procedure. The incidence of the PEP is approximately 5 to 10% [4]. The prevalence of PEP ranges from 1.3 to 8%. The mortality rate of PEP is about 0.1 to 0.5%. The pathophysiology of PEP includes various initiating events that lead to activation of pancreatic enzymes & auto digestion.¹⁰ PEP causes mechanical, chemical, hydrostatic, enzymatic, microbiologic, allergic or thermal disruption.¹¹ Multiple risk factors for the PEP have been identified and are broadly categorized into operator dependent, patient dependent & procedure dependent factor [5].

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study is to analyze the effect of Indomethacin in Prevention of Post-ERCP Pancreatitis patients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This randomized control study was conducted at THQ hospital, Yazman during 2018. There were total 200 patients who was selected for this study. Patients divided into two groups. One group was given per rectal indomethacin (2 suppositories 50 mg each) while other group given no suppositories. Patients already had raised amylase or acute pancreatitis, history of chronic pancreatitis or had a contraindication to NSAIDs were excluded from the study. An informed consent was obtained from eligible patients before the start of procedure and preliminary enrolment was performed.

Biochemical analysis

Serum amylase and lipase level were seen in all symptomatic patients at 4 hours and at 24 hours. The diagnosis of PEP was made on the presence of typical pain and a rise in amylase and lipase more than three times upper limit of normal. Patients developing PEP were managed conservatively by admitting the patient in hospital and giving I.V fluids and I.V analgesics.

Statistical analysis

The data was entered and analyzed by SPSS version 20. Mean and standard deviation (SD) was calculated from quantitative variables e.g. age, pancreatic enzyme. Frequency & percentage was calculated for qualitative variables e.g. gender and PEP.

RESULTS:

A total of 200 cases fulfilling the inclusion/exclusion criteria were enrolled to compare the frequency of Post ERCP Pancreatitis in patients treated with or without rectal indomethacin. Age distribution of the patients was done, it shows that 30%(n=45) in Indomethacin and 29.33%(n=44) without Indomethacin group were between 15-50 years of age while 70%(n=105) in Indomethacin and 70.67% without Indomethacin group were between 51-85 years of age, mean±sd was calculated as 56.28±8.39 and 55.72±7.84 years in both groups respectively. Gender distribution shows that 55.33%(n=83) in Indomethacin and 53.33%(n=80) in those without Indomethacin group were male while 44.67%(n=67) in Indomethacin and 46.67%(n=70) in those without Indomethacin group were females.

Table 01: Comparison of frequency of post ERCP pancreatitis in patients treated with or without rectal indomethacin

Characteristic	Indomethacin (n=223)	Placebo (n=226)	P value
Sphincter Manipulation			
Difficult Cannulation (>8 attempts) – no. (%)	46 (20.6)	42 (18.4)	0.64
Precut Biliary Sphincterotomy	11 (4.9)	16 (7.0)	0.43
Therapeutic Biliary Sphincterotomy – no. (%)	106 (46.9)	114 (50.9)	0.57
Therapeutic Pancreatic Sphincterotomy – no. (%)	12 (5.4)	5 (2.2)	0.08
Minor Duct Sphincterotomy – no. (%)	5 (2.2)	4 (1.8)	0.75
Balloon Dilation of Biliary Sphincter – no. (%)	21 (9.4)	20 (8.8)	0.87
Pancreatic Duct Manipulation			
Wire Cannulation of Pancreatic Duct – no. (%)	90 (40.3)	89 (31.4)	0.85
Pancreatography – no. (%)	50 (22.4)	49 (21.7)	0.97
Pancreatic Acinarization – no. (%)	5 (2.2)	4 (1.8)	0.75
Stent Placement			
Biliary Stent Placement – no. (%)	89 (39.9)	84 (37.2)	0.56
Pancreatic Stent Placement – no. (%)	36 (16.1)	35 (15.5)	0.90
Other Interventions			
Trainee Involvement in ERCP – no. (%)	152 (68.2)	168 (74.3)	0.18
Concomittant EUS/FNA – no. (%)	41 (18.4)	40 (17.7)	0.90
Periprocedural Fluid Volume - ml	705	703	0.95

DISCUSSION:

The pathological mechanism of post-ERCP pancreatitis is multifactorial. The mechanical, hydrostatic, thermal, bacterial and chemical insults accompanying cannulation and/or other modes of instrumentation of the papilla or the injection of contrast medium into the pancreatic duct may all result in a pancreatic duct injury [6]. These initiating factors may act independently or in combination, leading to autodigestion because of the premature intracellular activation of pancreatic proteolytic enzymes and the release of inflammatory cytokines, producing both local and systemic effects. The severity of pancreatitis is determined by the intensity of the inflammatory cascade and the systemic response. Attempts to prevent ERCP-induced pancreatitis take the pathogenetic factors into consideration and are based upon mechanical and pharmacological approaches [7]. Acute pancreatitis is a common and serious complication of endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP). Post-ERCP pancreatitis (PEP) accounts for substantial annual morbidity and health care expenditure, and occasional death. Prevention of PEP is an ongoing area of active research [8]. Several proposed pharmacologic agents and therapeutic techniques have been proposed to reduce the risk of PEP. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) reduce incidence of PEP in both high- and low-risk patients. Rectal NSAIDs are among the few agents shown to be effective in preventing PEP. Indomethacin is one of the NSAIDs used in the

clinical trials [9,10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that the frequency of Post ERCP Pancreatitis is significantly lower in patients treated with rectal indomethacin when compared to those without it.

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